

PARACHOR OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS AND THEIR CHEMICAL CONSTITUTIONS.

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Parachor of simple pyrone, dimethyl and diethylpyrones have been determined in ethyl acetate and nitrobenzene. The value in case of pyrone and diethylpyrone approaches more to the simple ring formulae and therefore must have the structure suggested by Deshpande (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 303), while dimethylpyrone should be represented by Collie's bridge-ring structure.

The structure of diacetylacetone has also been investigated. Its value of parachor in ethyl acetate approaches Collie's bridge-formulae.

The calculation of parachor for bridge-ring is carried on the basis that a bridge-ring is made of two rings each of five atoms and this finds justification from the authors' observations on isonitrosocampor which is known to contain bridge-ring. The value of its parachor in nitrobenzene is the same as calculated on the basis of the above assumption for the bridge-ring.

In our previous paper (*This Issue*, p. 149) we have shown from the results obtained with the low melting substances that, working under certain conditions, the parachor of a solid substance obtained from its solution is almost identical with that of the same substance worked above its melting point without any solvent; and these values are in turn identical with the calculated values corresponding to its accepted formula. We have now made use of this important observation in the case of certain organic compounds about whose structures two opinions have been held on chemical evidence. These compounds are the pyrone (I) and its dimethyl (II) and diethyl (III) derivatives and the 1:3:5 triketones related to the pyrones.

On fusion by means of baryta the dimethyl and diethylpyrones give iacetylacetone (IV) and the dipropionylacetone (V) respectively.

Structures (IV) and (V) have been established on chemical grounds by Deshapande, Dingankar and Kokil (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1934, 11, 595) and as (IV) and (V) result from (II) and (III) (Deshapande, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 303), the structures of the latter should be by inference what they are shown to be

Collie, however, on the ground that the pyrones form substitution products instead of addition products in spite of their containing two double bonds in the ring, thought that they are aromatic compounds, and must therefore contain three alternate double bonds in the ring. He therefore, assigned structure (VI) to dimethylpyrone and (VII) to diacetylacetone.

Parachor method has been used to ascertain whether the simple ring structure of pyrones by Deshapande (*loc. cit.*) or bridge-ring structure proposed by Collie is the correct one. Diethylpyrone (III) was chosen it being a liquid and therefore it was possible to obtain its parachor both in pure condition as well as in solution (Table I). The diethylpyrone was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Parachor calc. for (III) is 359.1 and that for Collie's formula is 370.

The following results were obtained for diethylpyrone dissolved in ethyl acetate. Parachor of the pure solvent was found to be 215.5 while with the formula it comes to 216.

TABLE I.

Diethylpyrone.

$\alpha = 0.203.$

Temp.	Density.	γ .	P_M .	P_X .
20°	0.9446	26.20	241.8	355
30	0.9336	25.39	242.7	359.5
40	0.9244	24.50	243.0	361
50	0.9152	23.63	243.3	362
60	0.9060	21.68	243.3	362

In the homologous series of pyrones there seems to be something unusual. The first member, the simple pyrone (I), is a solid melting at 32° and boiling at 215° at ordinary pressure. The next member, dimethylpyrone (II) is a high melting solid, m. p. 132°; but the next member, diethylpyrone (III), is a liquid, b. p. 115°-120°/10 mm. Chemical methods fail to explain this anomaly and it was thought interesting to apply the parachor method so as to throw any light on the structure of these substances.

The following results were obtained with pyrone (I) which was purified by two distillations, and was dissolved in ethyl acetate. Parachor calculated is 208.1 by simple ring formula.

TABLE II.

Pyrone.

Temp.	Density.	$\alpha = 0.129.$			$\alpha = 0.262.$			
		γ .	P_M .	P_X .	Density.	γ .	P_M .	P_X .
20°	0.935	24.71	212.4	188	0.9585	25.11	210.4	195
30	0.926	23.90	212.4	188	0.9510	24.23	210.1	193
40	0.917	23.09	212.7	191	0.9397	23.53	211.1	196
50	0.907	22.27	213.2	194	0.9300	22.68	211.3	197

These values are lower than those required either for the simple ring structure (I) or the bridge-ring structure (VI) except that the methyl group is replaced by H. Nevertheless the mean of the values in Table II is nearer the value for the simple ring structure and is much away from the value for the bridge-ring.

In the case of dimethylpyrone (II), which was purified by double crystallisation and which was dissolved in nitrobenzene (as its solubility in ethyl acetate is small), the following results were obtained.

TABLE III.

Dimethylpyrone.

Temp.	Density.	$\alpha = 0.164.$			Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_T.$
		$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_T.$				
50°	1.166	39.48	265.0	304	1.164	37.34	261.4	309
60	1.154	36.79	262.2	299	1.154	36.69	262.9	316
70	1.143	36.04	264.2	311	1.148	34.77	260.5	300

Table III also brings out the difference between the observed values and those calculated for either for the simple ring structure (II) or the bridge-ring structure, the observed values being higher than the values required for the structures (VI). Nevertheless the observed values are nearer that corresponding to simple ring structure.

Observed results indicate that pyrone (I) and diethylpyrone (III) are simple ring compounds, while dimethylpyrone (II), which comes in between the two, is a bridge-ring compound. This is probable when taken in conjunction with the fact that at ordinary temperature (about 32°) both pyrone and diethylpyrone are liquids, but dimethylpyrone is a high melting solid; or there is possibly some other kind of complexity in the molecule of dimethylpyrone. But it is significant that where chemical means could not explain why a middle member is a high melting solid, while its two neighbours are liquids, it could be explained at least to some extent by "parachor".

Dehydracetic acid (VIII) which is a pyrone was also studied and the following results were obtained when dissolved in nitrobenzene.

TABLE IV.

Dehydracetic acid.

Temp.	Density.	$P_{calc.} (VIII) = 374.1. \quad \alpha = 0.191$		
		$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_T.$
40°	1.204	40.92	272.7	372.2
50	1.196	38.9	272.4	370
60	1.186	38.19	272.2	369
70	1.177	36.91	272.0	368

The agreement between the value for the accepted formula (VIII) and the observed value is quite close.

Diacetylacetone, a 1:3:5-triketone, closely related to pyrones, was chosen for our study. Deshapande (*loc. cit.*) on chemical grounds gave it the formula (IV) but to which Collie has given the formula (VII). Table V shows the value of the parachor obtained for diacetylacetone dissolved in ethyl acetate.

TABLE V.
Diacetylacetone.

Temp.	Density.	γ .	P_M .	P_R .	Density.	γ .	P_{M1} .	P_R .
	$\alpha = 0.167.$				$\alpha = 0.183.$			
20"	0.9473	24.91	229.0	298	0.9363	25.71	235.9	324.6
30	0.9390	24.10	229.2	300	0.9287	24.91	235.8	324
40	0.9290	23.29	229.5	302	0.9212	24.02	235.3	322
50	0.9213	22.41	229.5	302	0.9093	23.29	236.5 ^a	328
60					0.9042	22.35	235.4	322

The value for structure (IV) is 334.2 and for the structure (VII) is 328. From these values alone it is difficult to decide in favour of either of the structures. The mean value observed from Table V is 324, which is fairly close to the value 328 corresponding to the bridge-ring structure. As diacetylacetone is derived from dimethyl-pyrone, it seems that the bridge-ring in the pyrone is retained when it changes to the corresponding triketone.

In the calculation of parachor for the bridge-ring such as shown in (VI) and (VII), a bridge-ring was assumed to be made of two rings each with five atoms. Whether such an assumption is justified must be tested by working with a substance in whose molecule the existence of a bridge-ring has been definitely proved. *iso*Nitrosocamphor (IX) having the same bridge-ring as in camphor was chosen for the purpose of experiment.

It could be purified by repeated crystallisations until the desired melting point is obtained. The following results were obtained with *isonitrosocamphor* dissolved in nitrobenzene.

TABLE VI.

isonitrosocamphor.

$P_{\text{calc}} = 438.$

Temp.	Density.	γ .	P_{H} .	P_{X} .	Density.	γ .	P_{H} .	P_{X} .	
	$\alpha = 0.118.$					$\alpha = 0.198.$			
50°	1.153	38.62	288.4	440	1.149	39.26	291.2	438	
60	1.144	37.34	288.3	440	1.141	37.87	290.7	436	
70	1.136	36.04	288.3	440	1.132	36.49	290.0	433	
80					1.120	35.30	290.5	435	

There is a close agreement between the values of parachor observed and found from the above tables and the value required for the formula (IX).

This proves that for the purpose of calculation of parachor of a substance containing a bridge-ring in its molecule, a bridge-ring may be taken to be equal to two simple rings.

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